

Thermodynamic and thermal comfort performance evaluation of two geothermal high-temperature cooling systems in the mediterranean climate

Henrikki Pieskä^{a,*}, Cong Wang^{a,b}, Behrouz Nourozi^a, Adnan Ploskić^{a,c}, Qian Wang^{a,d}

^a Division of Sustainable Buildings, School of Architecture and the Built Environment, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Brinellvägen 23, SE-10044, Stockholm, Sweden

^b College of Urban Construction and Safety Engineering, Shanghai Institute of Technology, 201418, Shanghai, China

^c Bravida Holding AB, Mikrofonvägen 28, SE-12637, Hågersten, Sweden

^d Uponor AB, Hackstavägen 1, SE-72132, Västerås, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

High-temperature cooling
Geothermal cooling
Indoor environment
Exergy
Building retrofit

ABSTRACT

The European Commission aims to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions of the European Union's building stock by 60% by 2030 compared with 1990. Meanwhile, the global demand for cooling is projected to grow 3% yearly between 2020 and 2050. High-temperature cooling systems provide cooling with lower exergy use than conventional cooling systems and enable the integration of renewable energy sources, and can play a crucial role in meeting the growing cooling demand with less energy use. The aim of this study is to analyse and critically evaluate two high-temperature cooling systems in terms of their energy and exergy use in a case study. We also consider thermal comfort performance, CO₂ emissions, and sensitivity to changing operating conditions. The two systems considered are a mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery combined with geothermal cooling (GeoMVHR) and a radiant cooling system with ceiling panels connected to the same geothermal cooling (GeoRadiant) system. The study is conducted using building energy models of a typical office building belonging to a three-building school complex located in Sant Cugat near Barcelona, Spain. IDA ICE 4.8 simulation software was used for the simulations. The results show that the two different installations can produce near-identical thermal comfort conditions for the occupants. The GeoRadiant system achieves this result with 72% lower electricity use and 60% less exergy destruction than the GeoMVHR system. Due to the higher electricity use, the CO₂ emissions caused by the GeoMVHR system are 3.5 times the emissions caused by the GeoRadiant system.

Nomenclature:

Abbreviations

ACH Air changes per hour [h⁻¹]
AHU Air handling unit

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: pieska@kth.se, pieska@kth.se (H. Pieskä).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2022.104738>

Received 15 February 2022; Received in revised form 18 May 2022; Accepted 30 May 2022

Available online 1 June 2022

2352-7102/© 2022 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

AIVC	Air Infiltration and Ventilation Centre
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers
CAV	Constant air volume
CDD	Cooling degree day
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
COP	Coefficient of performance
EC	European Commission
ECBCS	Energy Conservation in Buildings & Community Systems Programme
EU	European Union
HDD	Heating degree day
HTC	High-temperature cooling
HVAC	Heating, ventilation and air conditioning
IDA-ICE	Indoor climate and energy simulation software
IEA	International Energy Agency
MAD	Median absolute difference [–]
MVHR	Mechanical ventilation with heat recovery
PE100RC	Polyethylene pipe, resistant to cracks
PMV	Predicted mean vote [–]
PPD	Predicted percentage of dissatisfied [–]
SDG	Sustainable development goals
SFP	Specific fan power [W/(m ³ h)]
TABS	Thermally activated building systems
UN	United Nations
VAV	Variable air volume

Symbols

θ_{supply}	Temperature [°C]
\dot{Q}	Cooling heat flow [W]
Ex	Cumulative exergy destruction [Wh]
η	Efficiency [–]
P	Electrical power [W]
\dot{Ex}	Exergy destruction rate [W]
Δt	Length of time step [h]
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate [kg/s]
c_p	Specific heat capacity [J/(kg K)]
T	Temperature [K]
\dot{q}	Airflow rate [m ³ /s]

Subscripts

0	Ambient environment
a	Air
b	Brine
C	Cooling supplied to the conditioned space
CP	Cooling panels
CW	Cooling water circuit
dew, min	Lowest observed dew point in the building
el	Electricity
G	Ground
GC	Ground circuit
peak	Peak cooling power
ret	Cooling return water, brine or air
s	Cooling panel surface
supply (sup)	Cooling supply water, brine or air
w	Water

1. Introduction

In 2019, the European Commission (EC) launched The Green Deal, the European Union's (EU) sustainable growth strategy for making the union carbon-neutral by 2050 [1]. The United Nations' (UN) Sustainable development goals (SDGs) also call for limiting

the environmental effect of energy use [2]. As a result of this development, national building regulations in countries such as Spain have been gradually tightened. This poses challenges and opportunities for energy retrofit projects in the Spanish building stock, such as limiting buildings' cooling energy demands [3]. This has led to an increased interest in geothermal heating and cooling. A number of studies such as Saez Blasquez et al. [4] and Ramos-Escudero et al. [5] have found that geothermal heating and cooling can bring both economical and environmental benefits.

Demand for space cooling is constantly growing in Europe. Climate change is increasing temperatures globally [6], which has resulted in both increasing cooling demand in traditionally warm regions and the emerging requirement for cooling in regions where it has not previously been necessary. Larsen et al. [7] showed that in Europe, where heating demand is generally predicted to diminish due to climate change, cooling demand will grow by 25–50% between 2010 and 2050. Similarly, Hitchin et al. [8] predicted a 55–60% increase in installed cooling capacity in Europe between 2010 and 2025. The International Energy Agency (IEA) reached a similar conclusion, stating that space cooling is the fastest-growing building energy end-use globally [9]. They also note that global cooling demand is projected to grow at more than 3% a year between 2020 and 2050. Therefore, reducing cooling demand in individual buildings and improving the efficiency of cooling systems is essential for achieving global climate and energy goals.

An environmentally friendly way to improve cooling efficiency is high-temperature cooling (HTC). A number of studies and literature reviews have concluded that HTC systems can significantly decrease the primary energy use of a cooling system and improve chiller efficiency [10–12]. Furthermore, Kazanci et al. [13] noted that considering energy alone is insufficient to understand the cooling system's energy use. The exergy consumption of the system should be considered to analyse the system's performance holistically. It helps to determine major contributors to exergy destruction and thereby gives insight into which components need to be improved in order to improve the overall thermodynamic efficiency of the system. According to Energy Conservation in Buildings & Community Systems Programme (ECBCS) Annex 49, the minimum exergy requirement for space cooling is low, as the desired indoor temperature level is usually close to the ambient temperature [14]. Therefore, achieving low overall exergy consumption requires implementing HTC systems, which use supply water temperatures closer to room temperature than conventional cooling systems.

An HTC system uses cooling supply temperatures of 17 °C and above, while conventional cooling systems use supply temperatures of approximately 7 °C [15]. Seshadri et al. [15] showed that such HTC systems could decrease the cooling system's exergy loss resulting in a 29% increase in sensible cooling energy efficiency. Similar results were reported by Li et al. [16], who showed that a radiant cooling terminal achieved 30% higher exergy efficiency than a fan coil unit due to higher supply water temperature. Neither of these studies included the heat rejection system in their scope, which leaves a knowledge gap regarding the detailed exergy efficiency analysis of a complete system design.

Considering the potential improvements in exergy efficiency, Meggers et al. [17] concluded that low-exergy systems are vital on the path towards lowering greenhouse gas emissions in the building sector. Jangsten et al. [18] showed that implementing HTC systems in current building stock is realistic when combined with improved design and operation. Direct ground cooling has also been found beneficial with various types of terminal units, including both radiant and all-air systems, in mild climates by Arghand et al. [19,20]. However, Saber et al. [12] noted that, in hot and humid climates, a comfortable indoor condition can only be achieved under specific indoor and outdoor conditions when using supply water temperatures above the outdoor dew point. Therefore, when designing the cooling system, it is necessary to consider whether some thermal discomfort could be acceptable for the occupants or whether a dehumidification system is required.

Two main alternatives for cooling distribution within a building are air distribution and hydronic (pipe) distribution [21]. Air distribution generally refers to a system supplying cooled air through a centralised air handling unit (AHU), whereas hydronic distribution can be implemented with various kinds of terminal units (cooling panels, active chilled beams, thermally activated building systems (TABS) etc.). Both systems have merits, and a literature review by Karmann et al. [22] did not establish a clear preference between them in terms of perceived thermal comfort for the occupants. Therefore, the choice between the systems can be difficult for the project planner as it is likely to be case-dependent and should, therefore, be assessed carefully. Factors that need to be considered include installation cost, energy and exergy use, the availability of renewable energy sources, operational time and the resulting thermal comfort. The benefits of air distribution systems include lower installation costs [23], lower cooling load [11] and design flexibility in retrofit practice, whereas hydronic distribution systems provide more efficient heat transfer and lower draught risk [11]. Studying the systems in retrofit practice also limits the number of available terminal units, as e.g. TABS can realistically only be installed during construction phase and are not suitable for a retrofit project. The available supply temperature is also an important consideration, as some terminal units are better suited for HTC installations than others. The available supply temperature is one of the most important factors in determining the system's cooling capacity.

The two systems considered in this study are a mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery, combined with geothermal cooling (GeoMVHR), and a radiant cooling system with ceiling panels connected to the same geothermal cooling (GeoRadiant) system. Both are suitable for a retrofit project, as they can be installed on the existing building with minimal structural changes. They have also been found suitable for high-temperature cooling [20,24]. Both systems use a local ground heat exchanger (borehole) as the heat sink, where heat from the cooled space is rejected. Ground heat exchanger systems have been recognised to provide energy-efficient cooling with high exergy efficiencies. High exergy efficiency is reached because geothermal systems operate with lower exergy losses due to smaller temperature differences between energy supply and use than conventional alternatives that usually use fossil fuels [25].

1.1. Objectives

The EC has found that a significant barrier to retrofit projects' deployment is the end-users' and decision-makers' uncertainty of the project's benefits [26]. In this study, we aim to provide information for both groups about the relative merits of two easily implementable HTC retrofit system options. Both of the studied systems are renewable-based alternatives for conventional cooling systems

and can ensure good indoor air quality for the occupants. Using a local geothermal cooling source is beneficial from a primary energy use point of view for both systems. The main goals of this study are:

- To provide equivalent thermal comfort conditions in the studied space with the two systems in order to comprehensively assess the systems' thermodynamic performances in a comparable environment
- To evaluate the systems' thermal comfort performances, including an assessment of operative temperature, predicted mean vote (PMV), predicted percentage of dissatisfied (PPD) and indoor relative humidity, compared with the recommended levels in current international standards
- To evaluate the energy and exergy use of the system designs, including the heat rejection system and the auxiliary components that are necessary for the systems' function
- To assess the systems' ability to respond to a sudden step-change in cooling load and their resulting thermal comfort performance.

Special attention is given to analysing the distribution of exergy destruction in the different components of the cooling system, as exergy efficiency is the most critical performance metric for HTC systems. A clear understanding of where exergy losses occur is helpful for further developments in the field and future system design. The novelty of the present work lies in evaluating the current design recommendations in a practical case study. It provides a comprehensive analysis of the studied systems' performances including all the components of the system, and practical guidelines for decision-makers choosing between the studied systems in retrofit practice.

2. Methodology

2.1. Simulation software

In this study, we compare the performances of two geothermal cooling systems using dynamic building energy simulations. Simulations were performed with IDA-ICE 4.8 (Indoor Climate and Energy) simulation program, which is a common tool for studying cooling systems and their energy use [27]. The simulations with IDA-ICE follow the standard EN 15251:2007 [28]. The simulation program's accuracy was previously assessed in the IEA Solar Heating and Cooling Program, Task 22, Subtask C [29]. IDA-ICE was found to give accurate results and good agreement with reference programs. The models have also been found to accurately represent solar heat gains [30] and heat transfer from radiant cooling panels [31]. IDA-ICE uses variable time step approach, adapting the time step to the frequency content of the solution. The maximum time step used in the simulations was 1.5 h. The control systems in the program are idealised, meaning the controls are applied immediately when the triggering event occurs.

2.2. Building data inventory

This research is part of the Horizon 2020 project GEOFIT, and the studied location is one of the project's pilot sites. The case study building is a one-story office building with a floor area of 288 m² and a conditioned volume of 790 m³. The building is located in Sant Cugat near Barcelona in Spain and is a part of a three-building school complex. It is constructed of bricks, which is the prevalent building material in Spain [32], and can generally be regarded as a representative sample of the local building stock. Windows are equipped with internal PVC shutters to reduce incoming solar radiation, which is also typical in the studied climate. The external walls of the building have undergone an energy retrofit with increased insulation. Envelope parameters are presented in Table 1. Further details of this building and the local climate are presented in our previous study [33]. Pressure coefficients for the envelope were IDA-ICE's preset coefficients for a sheltered building, considering the surroundings of the studied building. The preset pressure coefficients used in IDA ICE are obtained from an Air Infiltration and Ventilation Centre (AIVC) report [34].

2.3. Boundary conditions for the simulation model

Wherever possible, the critical parameters for the building model were based on values obtained from the studied building. Where no data were available, the values were obtained from standards and relevant literature. The most important parameters and their sources are presented in Table 2. Further description regarding selecting the critical parameters can be found in our previous study [33].

To ensure the efficient long-term operation of the studied cooling systems, thermal balance in the ground must be considered. In the studied building, a ground-source heat pump system will be installed to provide heating for the building. Therefore, heat will be extracted from the borehole during heating operation and rejected into the borehole during cooling operation. To estimate the ratio of

Table 1
Thermal properties of the building envelope.

Item	Walls		Windows	
	Area [m ²]	U-value [W/m ²]	Area [m ²]	U-value [W/m ²]
North	83.0	0.27	15.8	2.90
South	87.0	0.27	25.2	2.90
East	66.1	0.27	1.92	2.90
West	66.1	0.27	1.96	2.90
Roof	301	0.26	-	-
Floor	288	2.9	-	-

Table 2

Parameters used in the cooling simulation. Data indicated with * were obtained from an on-site thermal response test and ** from the building owner.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Indoor temperature set point [35]	25.0	°C
Peak outdoor temperature [36]	31.4	°C
Mean ground temperature *	16.6	°C
Ground heat capacity *	2.11	MJ/(m ³ K)
Ground thermal conductivity *	1.96	W/(m K)
Borehole depth **	120	m
Brine (ethylene glycol) **	15%	-
Brine heat capacity **	3.90	kJ/(kg K)
Internal heat gain from lighting [37]	1.6	W/m ² floor area
Internal heat gain from appliances [38]	12	W/m ² floor area
Window solar heat gain coefficient [39]	0.76	-
Infiltration rate [40]	2.7	m ³ /(h m ² external surface) at 4 Pa
Number of occupants **	8	-
Activity level [35]	1.2	met
Clothing [35]	0.75 ± 0.25	clo
Occupied hours **	7–18	-

heat extracted and rejected to the borehole during a year, the average number of heating degree days (HDD) and cooling degree days (CDD) per month in Barcelona between 2011 and 2020 were calculated, based on Eurostat data [41]. The base temperatures used by Eurostat to calculate HDDs and CDDs are 15 °C and 24 °C, respectively. The average number of HDDs during the considered period (1730 in total) is roughly 11 times higher than the corresponding number of CDDs (151). Therefore, in the long term, the amount of heat extracted from the borehole will be higher than the amount of heat rejected to it. The result of this will be that the ground temperature around the borehole will decrease over time. This is beneficial for the passive cooling system, as the lower ground temperature will increase the cooling capacity of the cooling system. Similar results were reported by Belliard et al. [42] who studied a geothermal heating and cooling system in a similar climate. It should also be noted that in the studied case the highest cooling load occurs in August when the cooling system is shut down due to holidays. This further decreases the amount of thermal energy rejected into the borehole and thereby keeps it cool.

2.4. Details of the studied HTC systems

A passive geothermal energy system supplies the cooling for both studied systems. It consists of a ground heat exchanger in a vertical borehole. The borehole is 120 m deep, and the ground heat exchanger consists of a PE100RC double U-pipe with an outer diameter of 32 mm. By definition, the passive geothermal system does not include an active chiller, so all heat rejection takes place in the ground heat exchanger. The ground temperature below the ground surface layer is stable at 16.6 °C, according to a thermal response test conducted on the site in 2019. Due to non-ideal heat transfer, the lowest available cooling fluid temperature is estimated to be 18 °C. A similar approach was previously used by Pratiwi and Trutnevte [43]. Due to this high supply temperature, only HTC systems are viable for the studied passive cooling configuration.

System 1 is the GeoMVHR system, where the cooling energy is distributed in the building via cooled air through a central AHU. The studied GeoMVHR system is similar to the outdoor air pre-heating system investigated by Nourozi et al. [44] for winter use. The system here uses cooling brine from the borehole to cool the incoming supply air instead of heating it, as was done in the study by Nourozi et al. A similar concept was also studied by Ascione et al. [45], who found that direct geothermal cooling could be applied to pre-cool ventilation air. In this study, the studied system's cooling capacity is controlled by the volume of the supply airflow into the conditioned zones. Yao et al. [46] demonstrated that this control system is more energy-efficient than controlling the supply air temperature.

Fig. 1. Schematic design of the GeoMVHR system's cooling circuit. Numbered items are: 1) circulation pumps, 2) control 3-way valve, 3) fans and 4) AHU cooling coil.

Schematic designs of the cooling circuit and the ductwork designed for the central AHU are presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively. The ductwork design is based on the principles given by Nilsson [47], with the flow velocity in the duct limited to <5 m/s to avoid disturbing noise and the frictional pressure loss in the duct limited to 0.6 Pa/m. The total pressure loss in the ventilation system during design load is 160 Pa.

The system's supply airflow must be relatively high during the peak cooling loads to cover the cooling demand of the building. However, when the cooling demand is low, such a high supply airflow would result in unnecessarily high electricity use with little benefit to the occupants. Therefore, a variable air volume (VAV) system was used for this arrangement. The system control is based on the cooling demand, considering that a minimum supply airflow ensuring sufficient ventilation for pollutant removal is provided during the entire operational time. The maximum airflow rate in the system is 3.0 l/(s $m_{\text{floor area}}^2$) (3.4 ACH). A high airflow rate is required because the temperature difference between the cooling source and the room is relatively small, which needs to be compensated by increasing the airflow when the cooling load is high. The minimum necessary airflow for pollutant removal would be 0.15 l/(s $m_{\text{floor area}}^2$) (0.17 ACH) for unoccupied periods and 0.33 l/(s $m_{\text{floor area}}^2$) (0.37 ACH) for occupied time as given in EN 16798-1:2019 [35]. The value for occupied time is based on assuming that the building is very low polluting (due to its age) and category III of the standard for office buildings, requiring a ventilation rate of 0.2 l/(s $m_{\text{floor area}}^2$) + 4 l/(s per person).

However, in practice the availability of AHUs capable of delivering such a wide range of airflow rates is limited. Therefore, for the purposes of this study, we have modelled the system using manufacturer data of an AHU that can provide sufficiently high airflow during peak cooling use, but whose minimum airflow rate is considerably higher than the minimum required by the standard. This leads to unnecessarily high airflow rates when the cooling demand is low, as the minimum airflow rate of the selected AHU is 0.61 l/(s $m_{\text{floor area}}^2$) (0.68 ACH). The system is switched off during weekends and holidays but run on minimum airflow during the night for night ventilation. This has been found beneficial to all-air cooling systems by Woolley et al. [48]. In summer operation mode, the heat exchanger of the GeoMVHR system is bypassed, as the temperature difference between the supply and exhaust airflows is small and the amount of recovered energy would, therefore, be negligible.

System 2 is the GeoRadiant system, where the cooling is transferred to the occupants via ceiling cooling panels. The studied GeoRadiant system is similar to the one studied by Pieskä et al. [33]: cooling water, cooled by the borehole, is circulated in radiant ceiling panels, while a mechanical ventilation system controls the indoor air quality. The system's cooling capacity is controlled by the supply water temperature. Arghand et al. [20] found that this control arrangement produces the most favourable performance for a similarly designed system. The schematic design of the system's cooling circuit is presented in Fig. 3. The panel layout is designed to cover the maximum ceiling area available. As can be seen from the figure, the cooling panel area covers approximately 70% of the total ceiling area. The selected cooling panels' technical parameters are based on the manufacturer's actual performance data of cooling panel products available on the market [49]. With the lowest available supply temperature of 18 °C, the panels' cooling capacity with the design supply water flow of 17.2 kg/(h $m_{\text{panel area}}^2$) is 40 W/ $m_{\text{panel area}}^2$ based on manufacturer testing data. The panel system is equipped with a recirculation shunt to reduce the risk of condensation. The supply water temperature to the cooling panels is maintained at least 1 °C above the dew point temperature in the room with the highest condensation risk, based on the findings of Hao et al. [50]. During the unoccupied time, the cooling system is shut down and consequently the indoor temperature drifts following the outdoor temperature. The control principle of the supply water temperature is presented in Fig. 4. An AHU unit is modelled to provide acceptable indoor air quality for the building. Therefore, the AHU is sized to provide the hygiene requirement of 0.33 l/(s $m_{\text{floor area}}^2$) (0.37 ACH) corresponding to 10 l/(s per person) during working hours, with a 2-h start-up period before the occupancy starts [35]. The ventilation system's layout is equal to the one presented in Fig. 2, but the duct sizes were reduced to adjust for the lower supply airflow rate. The total pressure loss in the ventilation system during design load is 70 Pa. Night ventilation is not used, as its benefits for radiant

Fig. 2. Schematic design of the air duct network used for both systems in this study. FA denotes the room's floor area, WA window area and PA the cooling panel area (only for GeoRadiant system).

Fig. 3. Schematic design of the GeoRadiant system's cooling circuit. Numbered items are: 1) circulation pumps, 2) control shunt valve, 3) fans, 4) heat exchanger and 5) cooling panels.

Fig. 4. Control principle of the GeoRadiant system's supply water temperature.

cooling systems were found to be limited by Woolley et al. [48].

2.5. Sensitivity analysis

The HTC systems' performances were analysed under different environmental conditions to better understand their sensitivity to changing operating conditions. The baseline for all of the sensitivity analyses are the GeoMVHR and GeoRadiant systems respectively, operating as described above in section 2.4. Their performances are then compared with a number of interventions affecting the cooling load in the building or the cooling capacity of the systems.

The first considered intervention was to vary the amount of brine circulation in the ground heat exchanger. Brine flow in the ground heat exchanger affects the heat flow into the ground, affecting the system's cooling capacity. The impact of cooling power and brine flow variations on return brine temperature to the borehole is studied analytically. Four cooling power levels with associated brine flow rates, ranging from the peak cooling power to the low operational level are considered.

The second considered intervention was to introduce a drop arm awning to the windows to increase external shading. Shading reduces the solar heat gain in the building, and is one of the most common retrofit measures to reduce cooling load. Industry experience has indicated that this is a key external reduction of the cooling load [49]. In the baseline models (design brine flow, no added external shading), the windows are equipped with internal PVC shutters. The modelled increased shading was an external drop-arm awning controlled by IDA-ICE's standard solar radiation controller. This type of shading was chosen because it is one of the most common and efficient in the studied climate [51]. All of the configurations are compared in the Storage room zone. This is the zone with the highest peak operative temperature for the GeoRadiant system.

The modelled shading devices decrease the amount of solar radiation the building receives, thus decreasing the cooling energy demand's solar component by 2.5 MWh/m²_{floor area} (corresponding to 40% of the solar component in the baseline case) during the studied cooling season. The shading also reduces the peak cooling load due to solar radiation by 2.1 W/m²_{floor area} (=19%).

We also analysed the systems' responses to a sudden step-change in the cooling load. Two types of cooling load increasing interventions in a single zone were studied to evaluate this effect. In the first test, the number of occupants in the studied zone was increased fourfold for 4 h from 14:00 to 18:00. In the second test, the windows were opened to allow hot outdoor air to enter the zone freely for the same time frame. Both tests were conducted in the Teacher's room zone during the hottest day in the cooling period. This zone was chosen because it is the largest meeting room in the studied building and it has a large window area, which means the potential for significant fluctuations in the cooling load is considerable. Both tests are compared with a baseline of the systems' regular

operation. The results of the entire sensitivity analysis are presented in the Results section.

2.6. Building model validation

The building model was validated by comparing the simulated results with measured indoor temperature data from the studied building. The measurements were done after the envelope retrofit but before the installation of the cooling system. Therefore, the building used natural ventilation and had no cooling system during the measurement period, which is why the air temperature reached uncomfortable levels through most of the cooling season. This is reflected in the validation building model. The validation model was simulated using outdoor temperatures measured on-site. The measured period was between June 1 and September 5, 2019. Wind profile was obtained from the weather file [36]. A Netatmo climate station was used for the indoor air temperature measurements [52]. Simulated and measured indoor air temperatures as well as the outdoor temperatures used in the validation are presented in Fig. 5. The simulated and measured temperatures showed good agreement. The median absolute difference (MAD) between the two methods was 2.1%. The maximum absolute difference between the simulated and measured data was 1.4 °C. The small differences between the simulated and measured data suggest that the building model created in IDA ICE is valid. A more detailed description of the validation process is available in Ref. [33].

2.7. Electricity usage and exergy destruction in the evaluated cooling systems

Electricity use for pump and fan units was calculated to compare the two systems' exergy consumption. The required mass flow rates of brine in the ground circuit, cooling water in the cooling panel circuit and ventilation supply and return air were obtained from the simulations. These flow rates were then used to calculate pressure loss in each circuit of the cooling system. The pressure losses were calculated based on the system design presented in Fig. 2 and the cooling panel layout following the approach presented in Ref. [44]. Finally, the used pumps and fans were selected using manufacturer selection tools [53,54], respectively. The nominal power requirements for the selected pumps and fans are presented in Table 3. The total energy use of the pumps and fans during the evaluated cooling season is calculated based on each unit's simulated operation, taking into account unit efficiencies on partial load as given by the manufacturers. Exergy losses in other components, such as lighting or domestic hot water preparation, are not considered because they are the same in both scenarios.

Table 3 also presents the peak cooling power and efficiency of the systems, defined as the highest cooling power delivered divided by the highest electricity use, as well as the AHU's specific fan power (SFP) during peak cooling load. The GeoRadiant system provides 19% higher cooling power than the GeoMVHR system with 78% lower total electrical power. Therefore, it has a considerably higher peak cooling efficiency.

The exergy destruction resulting from electricity use in the auxiliary units was approximated based on their electrical efficiencies as, according to Rosen and Bulucea [55], electrical efficiency can be approximated as equivalent to exergy efficiency. Therefore, the useful energy is assumed to be equal to the exergy added to the fluid, and the waste energy is assumed to be equal to the exergy destruction. The exergy destruction Ex_{el} was calculated using Equation (1):

$$Ex_{el} = P \times (1 - \eta)\Delta t, \quad (1)$$

where P is the unit's electrical power during a simulation time step, η is the unit's electrical efficiency, and Δt is the length of the simulation time step.

Exergy destruction in the heat exchangers Ex_{GHEx} , Ex_{CP} , Ex_{AHU} (ground heat exchanger, cooling panels and AHU, respectively) was calculated based on the concept of cool exergy, presented by Kazanci et al. [56]. The exergy destruction in the ground heat exchanger Ex_{GHEx} was calculated using Equation (2):

Fig. 5. Measured and simulated mean air temperatures in the Storage room where the monitoring data were obtained, as well as the daily mean outdoor temperature used in the validation.

Table 3
Summary of the pump and fan powers for the studied scenarios.

Scenario	Peak pumping power (borehole)	Peak pumping power (ceiling panels)	Peak fan power (AHU)	Peak cooling power	Peak cooling efficiency	Peak SFP
	[W]	[W]	[W]	[W]	[–]	[kW/(m ³ h)]
GeoMVHR	280	-	1600	4700	2.5	2.2
GeoRadiant	280	96	42	5600	13	0.5

$$EX_{GHEs} = (\dot{E}X_G - \Delta\dot{E}X_{GC})\Delta t, \quad (2)$$

where

$$\dot{E}X_G = -\dot{Q}_G \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_G}\right) \quad (3)$$

and

$$\Delta\dot{E}X_{GC} = \dot{m}_b \times c_{p,b} \left[(T_{b,out} - T_{b,in}) - T_0 \times \ln \frac{T_{b,out}}{T_{b,in}} \right]. \quad (4)$$

Here $\dot{E}X_G$ is the cool exergy flow rate from the ground to the brine, $\Delta\dot{E}X_{GC}$ is the exergy consumption rate in the ground circuit, \dot{Q}_G is the rate of heat removed from the brine to the ground, T_g is the ground temperature, T_0 is the outdoor air temperature, \dot{m}_b is the brine mass flow rate in the ground heat exchanger, $c_{p,b}$ is the specific heat capacity of the brine, $T_{b,out}$ is the temperature of the brine coming out from the ground, and $T_{b,in}$ is the temperature of the brine going into the ground heat exchanger.

The exergy destruction in the cooling panels EX_{CP} was calculated using Equation (5):

$$EX_{CP} = (\Delta\dot{E}X_{CW} - \dot{E}X_C)\Delta t, \quad (5)$$

where

$$\dot{E}X_C = -\dot{Q}_C \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_s}\right) \quad (6)$$

and

$$\Delta\dot{E}X_{CW} = \dot{m}_w \times c_{p,w} \left[(T_{w,sup} - T_{w,ret}) - T_0 \times \ln \frac{T_{w,sup}}{T_{w,ret}} \right]. \quad (7)$$

Here $\dot{E}X_C$ is the exergy supplied from the cooling system to the indoor space, $\Delta\dot{E}X_{CW}$ is the exergy consumption rate in the cooling water circuit, \dot{Q}_C is the rate of heat transfer from the circulation water into the room, T_s is the average temperature of the ceiling cooling panel surface, \dot{m}_w is the water mass flow in the cooling panel circuit, $c_{p,w}$ is the specific heat capacity of water, $T_{w,sup}$ is the temperature of the cooling supply water going into the cooling panel circuit, and $T_{w,ret}$ is the temperature of the cooling return water coming out from the cooling panel circuit.

The exergy destruction in the AHU EX_{AHU} was calculated using Equation (8):

$$EX_{AHU} = (\Delta\dot{E}X_{w,AHU} - \Delta\dot{E}X_{a,AHU})\Delta t. \quad (8)$$

Here $\Delta\dot{E}X_{w,AHU}$ is the net exergy input by the cooling water to the AHU-cooling coil, and $\Delta\dot{E}X_{a,AHU}$ is the cool exergy flow rate to the supply air. Equation (7) can be adapted for both of these, replacing the values of mass flow, specific heat capacity, and respective temperatures from water to air where necessary.

3. Results

3.1. Thermal performance

To compare the energy and exergy use of the analysed HTC systems, they need to be evaluated under similar thermal comfort conditions. To ensure this, PMV and PPD values are compared between the two studied systems. Furthermore, the thermal comfort parameters of the building in its current state (without cooling and with natural ventilation) are given for comparison. PMV and PPD are defined in the ISO 7730 standard, PMV being an index on a 7-point thermal sensation scale predicting the mean value of the votes of a large group of persons, and PPD being a quantitative prediction of the percentage of thermally dissatisfied people who feel too cool or too warm. They are dependent on a number of factors including air and mean radiant temperatures, air velocity, the occupant's activity level and clothing. A full list of considered parameters and the equations for calculating PMV and PPD are available in the ISO 7730 standard [57].

The results are presented in Fig. 6, which presents the PMV and PPD data for every occupied room with both systems. The figure shows that the variance in PMV and PPD values between the two systems is very small except for the Secretary zone. The reason for this deviation is the low supply air flow rate and high cooling demand due to the large window area and small floor area. This limits the cooling capacity of the GeoMVHR system. Therefore, we can conclude that the systems are compared under the same conditions with similar perceived thermal comfort levels.

3.2. Sensitivity analysis

The results of the performed sensitivity analysis are presented in Fig. 7. The total duration of occupant discomfort for the baseline systems (design brine flow and no external shading) is 160 h for the GeoMVHR system and 145 h for the GeoRadiant system, corresponding to 24% and 22%, respectively, of the total occupied time of 671 h. Shading has a considerable effect on system performance reducing the occupants' discomfort time by 33–40 h during the cooling season for the GeoMVHR system. For the GeoRadiant system, the discomfort time is reduced by 51–67 h. In our study, occupant discomfort time is defined according to EN 16798–1:2019 Category B [35]. That is, when the operative temperature exceeds 26 °C, it is considered to cause thermal discomfort.

Decreasing the brine flow in the ground heat exchanger by 50%, from 0.8 kg/s to 0.4 kg/s, reduces the GeoMVHR system's cooling capacity during peak load by 0.80 W/m²_{floor area} (5%) and has a small effect on the operative temperature. The brine flow reduction increases the discomfort time by 11 h (7%) for the GeoMVHR system and 24 h (16%) for the GeoRadiant system. The effect of increasing the brine flow by 50%, from 0.8 kg/s to 1.2 kg/s, is even smaller, increasing the GeoMVHR system's cooling capacity by 0.52 W/m²_{floor area} and reducing discomfort time by 4 h (2%) for the GeoMVHR system and 3 h (2%) for the GeoRadiant system.

The temperature change of the brine in the ground heat exchanger was also calculated using the GeoRadiant system, as its peak cooling power is higher than the GeoMVHR system's. The temperature change was calculated for four cooling powers with varying brine flow rates. The results are presented in Fig. 8. The time-weighted average cooling power is calculated by omitting the time when the system is not in operation and then summing together the cooling power at each simulation timestep and dividing by the length of the time step. The time-weighted average cooling power is 5.2 W/m²_{floor area}, which is 27% of the peak cooling power given by the GeoRadiant system.

Fig. 6. PMV (a) and PPD (b) comparison between all considered rooms (as presented in Fig. 2). Number 1 denotes the values for the current situation with no cooling system, number 2 for the GeoMVHR system and number 3 for the GeoRadiant system. The horizontal lines inside the boxes denote the mean PMV or PPD values, the boxes themselves the two middle quartiles [25%–75%] of the data and the whiskers the most extreme data points excluding outliers.

Fig. 7. Duration curves of the operative temperature of (a) GeoMVHR-system and (b) GeoRadiant system during the occupied time. For normalised time, 1 = 671 h.

Fig. 8. Temperature change of the brine in the ground heat exchanger with varying cooling powers (\dot{Q}) and brine flow rates (\dot{m}).

With the time-weighted average cooling power and the baseline flow rate of 0.8 kg/s, the temperature change in the brine is less than 0.5 °C. Even when peak cooling power is supplied by the system, the temperature change is less than 2 °C. This is also shown in Fig. 9, which shows the supply and return temperatures during peak load conditions on July 24. The temperature difference between the supply and return of the cooling system remains mostly under 1 °C and peaks around 2 °C. Control strategy of the GeoRadiant system is described in detail in our previous publication [33]. The GeoMVHR system is a single-loop system, therefore, the supply temperature going into the building is equal to the temperature from the borehole and vice versa.

3.3. Evaluation of step-change response

As presented in section 2.5, the systems' responses to a sudden step-change in cooling load were analysed. These two tests gave different profiles of intermittent increased cooling load. The first test (increased occupancy) yielded a constant increase of the cooling load by approximately 17.5 W/m² floor area, whereas the second test (open window) initially yielded a significant cooling load increase of 50 W/m² floor area, which subsequently fell to 10 W/m² floor area as the outdoor temperature decreased. The results are presented in Fig. 10. The figure shows that opening the windows has a similar effect on both systems, as the operative temperature initially exceeds the baseline scenario by 0.63 °C for the GeoMVHR system and 0.70 °C for the GeoRadiant system, falling to 0.45 °C and 0.60 °C

Fig. 9. Supply and return temperatures of the borehole (blue) and building cooling system (red) during peak load conditions. The systems' operational times are shown with grey shading. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 10. Systems' reactions to a step-change in cooling load. The grey area represents occupied time.

respectively by the end of the intervention. However, the increased occupancy shows very different results for the two systems. With the GeoMVHR system, the effect of the disturbance is similar to the open windows test, with operative temperature exceeding the baseline initially by 0.57 °C, increasing to 0.87 °C at the end of the intervention. With the GeoRadiant system, the increased occupancy has a more pronounced effect. The operative temperature, indicated with a blue line in Fig. 10, initially exceeds the baseline by 0.83 °C, and the difference further increases to 1.49 °C at the end of the intervention.

3.4. Exergy and CO₂ emission analysis of the studied systems

Finally, the two HTC systems were evaluated regarding the CO₂ emissions produced due to their electricity use and their exergy consumption. The CO₂ emissions were calculated based on electricity use and the CO₂ intensity of the Spanish electricity mix (0.341 kg CO₂-eq/kWh according to Moro and Lonza [58]). The systems were divided into three circuits: ground heat exchanger, cooling panels and AHU. Both electrical and thermal exergy destruction in these circuits were calculated. Results are presented in Table 4 and Fig. 11. Table 4 shows that in the GeoMVHR system, majority the electricity use (71%), the related CO₂ emissions (71%) and the electrical (67%) and thermal (78%) exergy destruction occur in the AHU circuit. This is due to the high electricity use of the fans compared with the pumps. It should be noted that the operational time of the pumps and fans is longer than with the GeoRadiant system due to night ventilation.

Meanwhile, in the case of the GeoRadiant system, the vast majority of electricity use, CO₂ emissions and electrical exergy

Table 4

CO₂ emissions caused by electricity use and exergy destruction in the studied systems. The GeoMVHR system's total operational time is 1269 h (due to night ventilation) and the GeoRadiant system's 780 h during the cooling season.

	GeoMVHR				GeoRadiant			
	Electricity use	CO ₂ emissions	Cumulative electrical exergy destruction	Cumulative thermal exergy destruction	Electricity use	CO ₂ emissions	Cumulative electrical exergy destruction	Cumulative thermal exergy destruction
	[kWh/m ²]	[kg CO ₂ -eq]	[kWh/m ²]	[kWh/m ²]	[kWh/m ²]	[kg CO ₂ -eq]	[kWh/m ²]	[kWh/m ²]
Ground circuit	0.96	93.9	0.57	0.19	0.72	70.4	0.42	0.23
Cooling panel circuit	-	-	-	-	0.10	10.2	0.07	0.28
AHU circuit	2.34	230	1.17	0.70	0.11	11.1	0.07	-
Total	3.30	324	1.74	0.89	0.93	91.7	0.55	0.51

Fig. 11. Combined exergy destruction in the studied systems during one cooling season.

destruction (77%, 77% and 76%, respectively) occur in the ground heat exchanger. However, the highest thermal exergy destruction occurs in the cooling panel circuit. For both systems, the exergy destruction from electricity use is higher than the thermal exergy destruction. This is characteristic for an HTC system. Operating close to the ambient temperature level is advantageous for exergy efficiency. Fig. 11 presents the combined electrical and thermal exergy destruction for each circuit as well as the entire system. The figure shows that the GeoRadiant system's total exergy consumption is 59% lower than the GeoMVHR system's. However, it should be noted that in the studied case, the difference in the systems' thermal exergy performance will not affect the systems' operating costs, as the thermal energy is produced using free geothermal energy.

4. Discussion

The studied systems perform comparably in terms of provided thermal comfort for the occupants, and the systems' sensitivity to environmental disturbances is similar. Both systems can provide a comfortable indoor thermal climate for most of the considered cooling season. Analysing the results of those simulations, which included a sudden step-change in the cooling load, revealed that the high thermal mass of the GeoRadiant system enables it to cope with short impulses of increased cooling load. This dampening effect of high thermal mass to support cooling systems has been observed in several previous studies, e.g. Refs. [59,60]. By contrast, the lower thermal inertia of the GeoMVHR system makes this arrangement better at coping with a constant, medium-term increase in the cooling load. Similar results were found by Zhang et al. [61], who studied the resilience of various cooling systems in responding to disruptive events. They concluded that all-air systems have low to medium absorptive capacity (ability to absorb short disruptions such as power outages) but high adaptive capacity (ability to adjust performance to the disruption). Their results on the resilience of radiant cooling systems were inconclusive. This study further provides detailed quantifications of such impacts between the two systems. It should also be noted that while both systems reach the same peak operative temperature of 28.6 °C in the open windows scenario, the mean air temperature is higher with the GeoRadiant system (29.3 °C) than with the GeoMVHR system (28.7 °C) due to radiant cooling. This disparity means that the perceived thermal discomfort is slightly higher with the GeoRadiant system (PMV 1.3, slightly warm) than with the GeoMVHR system (PMV 1.2, slightly warm), given the studied operating strategies.

In the Mediterranean climate, high ambient humidity may lead to several risks, which must be considered. High indoor relative humidity affects the users' thermal comfort, causing discomfort [62]. Furthermore, it limits the cooling capacity of the GeoRadiant system as the supply water temperature must be maintained above the dew point temperature to avoid condensation. The systems' indoor relative humidity performance is presented in Fig. 12. The figure shows that indoor relative humidity is higher with the GeoRadiant system. The humidity is in the suggested range for 32% of the occupied time. The suggested range in EN 16798-1:2019 is between 40% and 60%, shown with green colour in Fig. 12. This results from the higher air exchange rate using the GeoMVHR system. In the GeoMVHR system, the supply air is also cooled, which results in some moisture condensing and the supply air being dryer than with the GeoRadiant system. This means using the GeoMVHR system offers thermal comfort benefits, and the indoor relative humidity is in the recommended range for 37% of the occupied time. Since indoor relative humidity exceeds the comfort level for most of the occupied time using both systems (65% for the GeoRadiant system and 60% for the GeoMVHR system), further measures for reducing indoor relative humidity should be considered. This could be achieved by improving the airtightness of the envelope to reduce infiltration of humid outdoor air and by dehumidifying the incoming ventilation air.

In contrast to the thermal comfort performance, the difference in the systems' electricity and exergy consumption is more notable. The higher pumping electricity use of the GeoMVHR system in the ground circuit results from the longer operating time required to reach the same thermal comfort performance as the GeoRadiant system. The pump is also operating in partial loads more often than in the case of the GeoRadiant system, which decreases its efficiency [53]. The same is true for ventilation fans. The VAV system in the GeoMVHR system is operating in partial loads for most of the cooling season. By contrast, the constant air volume (CAV) system in the GeoRadiant system is either operating at nominal load or switched off. This results in a higher fan efficiency compared with the

Fig. 12. The highest simulated indoor relative humidity in the building for each studied system. The black dashed lines represent the limits for category III (70%), category II (60%) and category I (40%) in EN 16798-1:2019. The green area represents the acceptable indoor relative humidity range, according to Sterling et al. [63]. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

GeoMVHR system. The average SFP of the AHU over the cooling season is 1.1 kW/(m³ h) for the GeoMVHR system and 0.5 kW/(m³ h) for the GeoRadiant system. SFP is calculated using Equation (9):

$$SFP = \frac{\sum P}{\dot{q}_{ret}}, \tag{9}$$

where $\sum P$ is the sum of electrical power used by the AHU and \dot{q}_{ret} is the return airflow rate.

It is also clear that air as the cooling transport medium is less efficient than water. The GeoMVHR system’s peak cooling power is 16% lower than the GeoRadiant system’s, even though the system’s electricity use in the AHU is 12 times higher than the combined electricity use of the cooling panel and ventilation systems in the GeoRadiant system. This difference is apparent in Fig. 13, which presents the daily average ventilation airflow rate using both systems. The difference between the ventilation rates is significant, especially in July, when the cooling demand is the highest. This observation supports the findings of Feustel and Stetiu [64]. It should be noted that the electricity use of the pumps and fans is sensitive to the pressure losses in their respective pipe and duct systems. The pipe system designs used in this study are based on the borehole system installed at the studied building and the cooling panel manufacturer’s recommendation [49]. The air duct design was done following the recommendations of Nilsson [47]. Using larger pipe and duct dimensions would result in lower operational electricity use but higher installation costs, which are usually negligible in the long-term perspective. The current study clearly shows that high-temperature cooling systems need to be operated with small temperature differences. In order to achieve this efficiently, their distribution systems need to be designed diligently. Here we followed the current design recommendation and used a U-pipe of outer diameter of 32 mm. This resulted in a pumping power need of 277 W for the brine circuit, as shown in Table 3. This electricity power need could be decreased by a factor of 4.6 by increasing the pipe diameter by

Fig. 13. Daily average ventilation airflow rates during the cooling season for the studied systems.

10 mm. This in turn would significantly increase the exergy efficiency and decrease the CO₂ emissions caused by the cooling system. The same holds for GeoMVHR. This fact clearly illustrates the importance of a proper engineering design of high temperature cooling systems. The peak heat rejection rate into the borehole was 40 W/m_{borehole} for the GeoMVHR and 47 W/m_{borehole} for the GeoRadiant system. These rates agrees with field measurement data recently reported by Ramos-Escudero et al. who reported heat rejection rates ranging between 38 and 85 W/m_{borehole} in similar locations [5]. This further confirms the validity of our results.

This study focuses on comparing the performances of the studied systems, whose lifecycle cost and lifecycle assessment remain a subject of further overall sustainability evaluations, which should be considered when making final investment decisions. It should also be noted that both systems have limited cooling capacity due to the high supply temperature and the requirement to avoid condensation. Therefore, the cooling system designs investigated here aim to optimise the use of the available heat resource. The study aims to quantify the strengths and weaknesses of the studied HTC systems under the same boundary conditions and offer recommendations for future design guidance and reference. Table 5 presents a comparative assessment of the systems' performances in different aspects. The results are valid for the studied set of boundary conditions, and the application of the studied systems in other environments should be done considering local conditions such as climate and cooling load. The long-term effect of operating the cooling system on ground temperature and the performance of the GeoRadiant system once it has been installed will also be a focus of our future work.

5. Conclusions

In this study, the performances of two types of high-temperature cooling (HTC) systems are examined, a GeoMVHR system and a GeoRadiant system, both supplied by passive geothermal cooling energy in the Mediterranean climate. The primary objective of the study was to evaluate the energy and exergy use of two different design solutions under similar thermal comfort conditions. Responses to a step-change in cooling load were also analysed. Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

- The evaluated HTC systems provide equal levels of perceived thermal comfort, maintaining the operative temperature below 26 °C for 76% (GeoMVHR) and 78% (GeoRadiant) of the cooling season (671 h of total occupied time) in Barcelona.
- The systems are not sensitive to changes in the brine flow rate in the ground heat exchanger. However, reducing the cooling load by increasing shading can decrease thermal discomfort time by 22–25% with the GeoMVHR system and by 36–40% with the GeoRadiant system, respectively. The studied shading devices also reduced the required cooling energy by 40% during the whole cooling season and the peak cooling load caused by solar radiation by 19%.
- The GeoMVHR system consumes 3.5 times as much electricity, causing 3.5 times as much CO₂ emission as the GeoRadiant system. The GeoMVHR system also consumes 2.5 times as much exergy. The higher electricity use is mainly caused by less efficient heat transportation leading to increased ventilation airflow rate. The higher exergy consumption is caused by the lower efficiency of fans and pumps on partial loads.
- The higher ventilation airflow rate of the GeoMVHR system offers a thermal comfort benefit due to lower indoor relative humidity. The indoor relative humidity is in the recommended range for 37% of the occupied time with the GeoMVHR system and 32% of the occupied time with the GeoRadiant system.
- The GeoMVHR system offers better performance in situations where relative indoor humidity is a major concern, and when large variances in the cooling load are to be expected. The GeoRadiant system performs better when the cooling load is stable and low exergy consumption or CO₂ emissions are required.
- HTC systems need to be operated with relatively high mass flows to compensate for the small temperature differences in every part of the system. Pressure losses must, therefore, be carefully considered when designing the pipe and air duct networks. Increasing the diameter of pipes and air ducts mitigates pressure losses and the effect of larger mass flows on the electricity use of fans and pumps, thus decreasing exergy consumption in the cooling system.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, H.P., Q.W. and A.P.; methodology, H.P.; software, H.P. and C.W.; validation, H.P.; formal analysis, H.P., C.W., B.N., Q.W. and A.P.; investigation, H.P., C.W. and B.N.; resources, Q.W.; data curation, H.P. and C.W.; writing—original draft preparation, H.P.; writing—review and editing, Q.W., C.W., A.P.; visualization, H.P.; supervision, Q.W. and A.P.; project administration, Q.W.; funding acquisition, Q.W. and A.P.

Table 5

Main results of the comparisons; (+) advantage, (-) disadvantage, (0) neutral.

	GeoMVHR	GeoRadiant
Thermal comfort	Equal (0)	Equal (0)
Thermal exergy use	Higher (-)	Lower (+)
Electrical exergy use	Higher (-)	Lower (+)
CO ₂ emissions	Higher (-)	Lower (+)
Sensitivity to changing operating conditions	Equal (0)	Equal (0)
Absorptive capacity to respond to a step-change in the cooling load	Lower (-)	Higher (+)
Adaptive capacity to respond to a step-change in the cooling load	Higher (+)	Lower (-)
Indoor relative humidity	Lower (+)	Higher (-)

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The project has received funding from the EU H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 792210. Development Fund of the Swedish Construction Industry (SBUF), project number: 13776 and Swedish Energy Agency (Energimyndighet), project number: 42650-3 have also contributed to the realization of the project. Special thanks to industry partner Uponor for providing technical support and data inputs, municipal partner Ajuntament Sant Cugat for providing building data and user information and Professor Emeritus Sture Holmberg and Associate Professor Saqib Javed for their valuable comments. We would also like to extend our thanks to the anonymous reviewers, who have helped to improve the quality of the article.

References

- [1] European Commission, The European Green Deal Sets Out How to Make Europe the First Climate-Neutral Continent by 2050, Boosting the Economy, Improving People's Health and Quality of Life, Caring for Nature, and Leaving No One behind, December 2019, European Commission Press Room, 2019, pp. 11–12 [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_19_6691.
- [2] R. Khosla, et al., Cooling for sustainable development, *Nat. Sustain.* 4 (3) (2021) 201–208, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-020-00627-w>.
- [3] L.M. López-Ochoa, J. Las-Heras-Casas, P. Olasolo-Alonso, L.M. López-González, Towards nearly zero-energy buildings in Mediterranean countries: fifteen years of implementing the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive in Spain (2006–2020), *J. Build. Eng.* 44 (Dec. 2021), 102962, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2021.102962>.
- [4] C.S. Blázquez, A.F. Martín, I.M. Nieto, D. González-Aguilera, Economic and environmental analysis of different district heating systems aided by geothermal energy, *Energies* 11 (5) (2018), <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11051265>.
- [5] A. Ramos-Escudero, M.S. Garcia-Gascales, J.F. Urchueguía, Evaluation of the shallow geothermal potential for heating and cooling and its integration in the socioeconomic environment: a case study in the region of Murcia, Spain, *Energies* 14 (5740) (2021).
- [6] V. Masson-Delmotte, et al., Summary for Policymakers, IPCC, 2018.
- [7] M.A.D. Larsen, S. Petrović, A.M. Radoszynski, R. McKenna, O. Balyk, Climate change impacts on trends and extremes in future heating and cooling demands over Europe, *Energy Build.* 226 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.110397>.
- [8] R. Hitchin, C. Pout, P. Riviere, Assessing the market for air conditioning systems in European buildings, *Energy Build.* 58 (2013) 355–362, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2012.10.007>.
- [9] IEA, Is Cooling the Future of Heating? IEA, Paris, 2020. <https://www.iea.org/commentaries/is-cooling-the-future-of-heating>. (Accessed 22 December 2020).
- [10] J. Babiak, B.W. Olesen, D. Petras, Low temperature heating and high temperature cooling, REHVA Guidebook No 7 (2009).
- [11] K.N. Rhee, B.W. Olesen, K.W. Kim, Ten questions about radiant heating and cooling systems, *Build. Environ.* 112 (2017) 367–381, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.11.030>.
- [12] E.M. Saber, K.W. Tham, H. Leibundgut, A review of high temperature cooling systems in tropical buildings, *Build. Environ.* 96 (Feb. 2016) 237–249, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2015.11.029>.
- [13] O.B. Kazanci, M. Shukuya, B.W. Olesen, Exergy performance of different space heating systems: a theoretical study, *Build. Environ.* 99 (Apr. 2016) 119–129, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.01.025>.
- [14] D. Schmidt, Low exergy systems for high-performance buildings and communities, *Energy Build.* 41 (3) (2009) 331–336, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2008.10.005>.
- [15] B. Seshadri, A. Rysanek, A. Schlueter, High efficiency 'low-lift' vapour-compression chiller for high-temperature cooling applications in non-residential buildings in hot-humid climates, *Energy Build.* (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.01.028>.
- [16] Z. Li, D. Zhang, X. Chen, C. Li, A comparative study on energy saving and economic efficiency of different cooling terminals based on exergy analysis, September 2019, *J. Build. Eng.* 30 (2020), 101224, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2020.101224>.
- [17] F. Meggers, M. Mast, H. Leibundgut, The missing link for low exergy buildings: low temperature-lift, ultra-high COP heat pumps, *Proc. Clima 2010 Sustain. Energy Use Build.* (2010). December 2013, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259284556_The_missing_link_for_low_exergy_buildings_low_temperature-lift_ultra-high_COP_heat_pumps.
- [18] M. Jangsten, J. Kensby, J.-O. Dalenbäck, A. Trüschel, Survey of radiator temperatures in buildings supplied by district heating, *Energy* 137 (Oct. 2017) 292–301, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.07.017>.
- [19] T. Arghand, S. Javed, A. Trüschel, J.O. Dalenbäck, A comparative study on borehole heat exchanger size for direct ground coupled cooling systems using active chilled beams and TABS, *Energy Build.* 240 (Jun. 2021), 110874, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.110874>.
- [20] T. Arghand, S. Javed, A. Trüschel, J.O. Dalenbäck, Control methods for a direct-ground cooling system: an experimental study on office cooling with ground-coupled ceiling cooling panels, *Energy Build.* 197 (2019) 47–56, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.05.049>.
- [21] Heating, Ventilation, and Air-Conditioning SYSTEMS and EQUIPMENT, ASHRAE Handbook, 2012.
- [22] C. Karmann, S. Schiavon, F. Bauman, Thermal comfort in buildings using radiant vs. all-air systems: a critical literature review, *Build. Environ.* 111 (2017) 123–131, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.10.020>.
- [23] S.A. Mumma, Chilled ceilings in parallel with dedicated outdoor air systems: addressing the concerns of condensation, capacity, and cost, 15 cm, *Build. Eng.* 108 (2) (2002) 220–231.
- [24] C. Wang, Q. Wang, B. Nourozi, H. Pieskä, A. Ploskić, Evaluating the cooling potential of a geothermal-assisted ventilation system for multi-family dwellings in the Scandinavian climate, *Build. Environ.* 204 (Oct. 2021), 108114, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2021.108114>.
- [25] R. Sangi, D. Müller, Dynamic modelling and simulation of a slinky-coil horizontal ground heat exchanger using Modelica, *J. Build. Eng.* 16 (Mar. 2018) 159–168, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2018.01.005>.
- [26] European Commission, Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions: a renovation wave for Europe - greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives, Off. J. Eur. Union (2020) 26.
- [27] M.A. Hassan, O. Abdelaziz, Best practices and recent advances in hydronic radiant cooling systems – Part II: simulation, control, and integration, *Energy Build.* 224 (Oct. 2020), 110263, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.110263>.
- [28] A.B. Equa Simulation, Validation of IDA Indoor Climate and Energy 4.0 with Respect to CEN Standards EN 15255-2007 and EN 15265-2007, 2010.
- [29] IEA, M. Achermann, G. Zweifel, RADTEST – Radiant Heating and Cooling Test Cases, 2003.
- [30] D. Mazzeo, N. Matera, C. Cornaro, G. Olivetti, P. Romagnoni, L. De Santoli, EnergyPlus, IDA ICE and TRNSYS predictive simulation accuracy for building thermal behaviour evaluation by using an experimental campaign in solar test boxes with and without a PCM module, *Energy Build.* 212 (Apr. 2020), 109812, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.109812>.
- [31] M.R. Krusaa, C.A. Hviid, Combining suspended radiant ceiling with diffuse ventilation – numerical performance analysis of low-energy office space in a temperate climate, *J. Build. Eng.* 38 (Jun. 2021), 102161, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2021.102161>.

- [32] J. Feijó-Muñoz, R.A. González-Lezcano, I. Poza-Casado, M.Á. Padilla-Marcos, A. Meiss, Airtightness of residential buildings in the Continental area of Spain, November 2018, *Build. Environ.* 148 (2019) 299–308, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2018.11.010>.
- [33] H. Pieskä, A. Ploskic, Q. Wang, Design requirements for condensation-free operation of high-temperature cooling systems in mediterranean climate, *Build. Environ.* 185 (May, 2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2020.107273>.
- [34] M. Orme, M. Liddament, A. Wilson, Numerical data for air infiltration & natural ventilation calculations, *Tech. Note AIVC 44* (1994) 82–87.
- [35] EN 16798-1:2019, *Energy Performance of Buildings – Ventilation for Buildings – Part 1: Indoor Environmental Input Parameters for Design and Assessment of Energy Performance of Buildings Addressing Indoor Air Quality, Thermal Environment, Lighting and Acoustics – Module M1*, 2019.
- [36] Y.J. Huang, F. Su, D. Seo, M. Krarti, Development of 3012 IWECE2 weather files for international locations (RP-1477), *Build. Eng.* 120 (2014) 340–355.
- [37] B. Gayral, LEDs for lighting: basic physics and prospects for energy savings, *Compt. Rendus Phys.* 18 (7–8) (Sep. 2017) 453–461, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CRHY.2017.09.001>.
- [38] K. Ahmed, A. Akhondzada, J. Kurnitski, B. Olesen, Occupancy schedules for energy simulation in new prEN16798-1 and ISO/FDIS 17772-1 standards, *Sustain. Cities Soc.* 35 (Nov. 2017) 134–144, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2017.07.010>.
- [39] J. Carmody and B. Crooks, “Selecting Windows Based on Annual Energy Performance,” in https://www.aceee.org/files/proceedings/1996/data/papers/SS96_Panel10_Paper02.pdf, pp. 7–13.
- [40] A. Litvak, D. Boze, M. Kilberger, Airtightness of 12 non residential large buildings results from field measurement studies, L, Mark. *Oppor. Adv. Vent. Technol. 22nd Air Infiltration Vent. Cent. Conf.* (2001), <https://www.aivc.org/resource/airtightness-12-non-residential-large-buildings-results-field-measurement-studies>.
- [41] Eurostat the Statistical Office of the European Union, *Energy Statistics - Cooling and Heating Degree Days*, 2021. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/nrg_chdd_esms.htm. (Accessed 6 December 2021).
- [42] M. Belliardi, N. Cereghetti, P. Caputo, S. Ferrari, A method to analyze the performance of geocooling systems with borehole heat exchangers. *Results in a monitored residential building in southern alps*, *Energies* (14) (2021) 7407.
- [43] A.S. Pratiwi, E. Trutnevte, Life cycle assessment of shallow to medium-depth geothermal heating and cooling networks in the State of Geneva, *Geothermics* 90 (Feb. 2021), 101988, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GEOTHERMICS.2020.101988>.
- [44] B. Nourozi, Q. Wang, A. Ploskić, Maximizing thermal performance of building ventilation using geothermal and wastewater heat, September 2018, *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 143 (2019) 90–98, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.12.025>.
- [45] F. Ascione, M. Borrelli, R.F. De Masi, G.P. Vanoli, Hourly operational assessment of HVAC systems in Mediterranean Nearly Zero-Energy Buildings: experimental evaluation of the potential of ground cooling of ventilation air, *Renew. Energy* 155 (Aug. 2020) 950–968, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RENENE.2020.03.180>.
- [46] Y. Yao, Z. Lian, W. Liu, Z. Hou, M. Wu, Evaluation program for the energy-saving of variable-air-volume systems, *Energy Build.* 39 (5) (2007) 558–568, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2006.09.010>.
- [47] P.E. Nilsson, *Achieving the Desired Indoor Climate*, Studentlitteratur AB, 2003.
- [48] J. Woolley, S. Schiavon, F. Bauman, P. Raftery, Side-by-side laboratory comparison of radiant and all-air cooling: how natural ventilation cooling and heat gain characteristics impact space heat extraction rates and daily thermal energy use, *Energy Build.* 200 (Oct. 2019) 68–85, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2019.07.020>.
- [49] Uponor Corporation, *Build on Uponor with Varicool Carbon*, 2017, pp. 1–12 [Online]. Available: <https://www.uponor.com/products/ceiling-heating-and-cooling/varicool-carbon-a-and-s-cooling-panel>.
- [50] X. Hao, G. Zhang, Y. Chen, S. Zou, D.J. Moschandreas, A combined system of chilled ceiling, displacement ventilation and desiccant dehumidification, *Build. Environ.* (2007), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2006.08.020>.
- [51] J. Jorge, J. Puigdomènech, J.A. Cusidó, A practical tool for sizing optimal shading devices, *Build. Environ.* 28 (1) (1993) 69–72, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1323\(93\)90007-P](https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1323(93)90007-P).
- [52] Netatmo weather station.” <https://www.netatmo.com/en-us/weather/weatherstation> (accessed Apr. 25, 2020).
- [53] Grundfos, “Grundfos product selection tool.” product-selection.grundfos.com (accessed Nov. 24, 2020).
- [54] FläktWoods, “Acon AHU sizing tool.” <http://acon.flaktgroup.com> (accessed Nov. 24, 2020).
- [55] M.A. Rosen, C.A. Bulucea, Using exergy to understand and improve the efficiency of electrical power technologies, *Entropy* 11 (4) (2009) 820–835, <https://doi.org/10.3390/e11040820>.
- [56] O.B. Kazanci, M. Shukuya, B.W. Olesen, Theoretical analysis of the performance of different cooling strategies with the concept of cool exergy, *Build. Environ.* (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.02.013>.
- [57] ISO 7730:2005(E), *Ergonomics of the Thermal Environment — Analytical Determination and Interpretation of Thermal Comfort Using Calculation of the PMV and PPD Indices and Local Thermal Comfort Criteria*, 2005.
- [58] A. Moro, L. Lonza, Electricity carbon intensity in European Member States : impacts on GHG emissions of electric vehicles, November 2016, *Transport. Res. Part D* 64 (2018) 5–14, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.07.012>.
- [59] B. Lehmann, V. Dorer, M. Koschensch, Application range of thermally activated building systems tabs, *Energy Build.* 39 (5) (2007) 593–598, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2006.09.009>.
- [60] B.W. Olesen, M. De Carli, M. Scarpa, M. Koschensch, Dynamic evaluation of the cooling capacity of thermo-active building systems, *Build. Eng.* 112 (2006) 350–357.
- [61] C. Zhang, et al., Resilient cooling strategies – a critical review and qualitative assessment, *Energy Build.* 251 (Nov. 2021), 111312, <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2021.111312>.
- [62] S. Jahan, T. Hassan, M. Kumar, A. Baten, S. Hossen, Status of thermal comfort in naturally ventilated university classrooms of Bangladesh in hot and humid summer season, *March, J. Build. Eng.* 32 (2020), 101700, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobee.2020.101700>.
- [63] E.M. Sterling, A. Arundel, T.D. Sterling, Criteria for human exposure to humidity in occupied buildings, *Build. Eng.* 91 (1985).
- [64] H.E. Feustel, C. Stetiu, Hydronic radiant cooling - preliminary assessment, *Energy Build.* 22 (1995) 193–205.